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DEVELOPING OF THE READING COMPETENCE OF STUDENTS BETWEEN HIGHER MEDICAL INSTITUTIONS

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Abstract: Most academic and professional information is available through publications in English. The ability to read in English is widely seen as an essential skill for university students in many countries, like Mexico, where English is a foreign language. However, students often have problems when reading these publications because their reading ability is not good enough.

Keywords: Reading competence, Higher Medical Institutions, Studies of Good Language Learners, ESP, reading skills, EFL classes, Language Teaching Centre, Economy, In the United States, based reading.

Introduction Most of the universities all around the world aim to provide qualified professionals with the necessary competence to perform successfully in the area of their preparation. Currently, basic education is including English as part of the curriculum from preschool to elementary education. There is a necessity in the country to learn a second language in order to get better job opportunities nationally and internationally. Even when students are conscious of the advantages of knowing a language, many consider this subject only as compulsory, and nothing more. At this time, they really need to improve their English: they need to read literature related to their field of expertise while they are in their major and it is indisputable that most of the specialized literature is in English; they also need the language after graduating for continuing their education. It is also indisputable that a large percentage of the research production in the world is in English and furthermore, many students who finish their major continue studying their master's degree, and for this it is necessary in most cases to have a working knowledge of English. Learning English is necessary for students and they must consider it as a fundamental part of their preparation. Reading is a multifaceted process that develops only with practice. There are certain aspects of reading, such as fluency and word recognition which, depending on the learner's competence, can take some time to be developed. These basics must be mastered but at

the same time reading comprehension should be emphasized in the process. This means reading ability is really important, specifically for university students who will need this ability in their studies and in their future professional development or postgrad studies. It is generally known, that most of the time students use many different strategies that help them improve pronunciation, grammar, writing, reading, and listening during their English language learning process. Researchers have been studying the way students learn a language; specifically, what strategies language learners use while they are learning; this type of study has now been formalized as the study of language learning strategies (LLS). Oxford (1990) found that students who learn with ease are those who use a wide variety of learning strategies. Studies of Good 2 Language Learners (GLL) started when research focused on identifying what students do when learning and the characteristics that made them have good results. The purpose of most research was to find the strategies that good learners used. Therefore, teacher would know how to facilitate the language learning process to the students who found it difficult to learn a foreign language. Shen & Wu (2009) found that efficient readers can extract from what they are reading what is important for the particular task they are involved in, and they can do this in an efficient way. Educational researchers have also found a strong correlation between reading and vocabulary knowledge. Students who have a large vocabulary are usually good readers. Chamot et al. (1999) stated that those learners who are conscious of their own strategies are more able to manipulate their own learning and thus, increase the possibilities in succeeding as language learners. Based on my experience as a language teacher, when students are in the classroom, their “learning” is reduced to coming to class, trying to memorize the vocabulary, taking the exam and passing the subject. The world in which students will live and work, is clearly different from the ones in which their parents and teachers grew up. Economy, technology and many social changes are transforming the world that is more interconnected and interdependent. Globalization is triggering new concerns and demands a new kind of graduate. At the dawn of the 21st century we are recasting our understanding of economics, communication, security, cultural identity, citizenship, and the environment. There is an increasing call for a more powerful and relevant learning in response to these new demands and opportunities (Gardner, 2007; Reimers, 2009; Stewart, 2007). Students need to be prepared to be global citizens capable of understanding an ever increasing number of scientific texts that are published in English. They need to learn to acquire knowledge and develop skills and competences. Additionally, they have to develop higher order thinking skills, such as critical thinking, considered necessary for succeeding in the 21st century. In the United States, the commission on reading in the national council of teachers of English (2008) stated that reading strategies have a purpose and represent cognitive actions that students resort to when they are reading in order to create and retain meaning. For the commission, reading successfully goes well beyond fluency and word recognition and depends heavily upon understanding the text. Since reading is a meaning-making task, any action used to 3 enhances student understanding helps to create more effective readers. Also, according to the commission, reading strategies are often categorized as those behaviors designed to help students before, during, and after they read.

One of the purposes of this investigation was to introduce and measure the effectiveness of a training approach to the teaching of reading strategies through the use of texts related to students' major. With this, students would be aware of the strategies they can use when reading and use them according to their purpose of reading. The most efficient way to enhance learner awareness is to provide strategy training - explicit instruction in how to apply language learning strategies - as part of the foreign language curriculum.

On the whole, reading can become an easier and useful skill for students; also it can have an important role in the learning process of the English language. Furthermore, it is a key component for understanding written language. At the same time, the application of reading strategies may help

students to transform reading into an efficient tool that they can use according to the way they are taught and the reason for that.

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